

Screening of the antibacterial and anti-biofilm effect of multifloral honey against multidrug-resistant *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*

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Summary

In this study, seven Algerian honey samples were assessed for their antibacterial activity on the growth, viability, and biofilm formation of clinical strains of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolated from infected wounds. The evaluation of the antibacterial activity of honey samples was determined by both well assay and micro-broth dilution assay. The effect of honey samples on the viability of *P. aeruginosa* was evaluated by a time-kill assay. The anti-biofilm effect was performed by using 96-well plates.

The results revealed that Algerian honey exhibit an antibacterial effect against *P. aeruginosa*. The inhibitory diameters ranged from $14.97 \pm 3.88\text{mm}$ to $27.98 \pm 3.19\text{mm}$. Minimum inhibitory

concentration (MIC) values were in the range of 10 to 40% (w/v). The MIC₅₀ varied from 7.88 % (w/v) for honey sample 5 to 18.5% (w/v) for honey sample 7 and the MIC₉₀ was in the range of 18.78 to 38.35% (w/v). The minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) values ranged from 22.43±6.62% (w/v) to 39.51±8.35% (w/v) and the MBC/MIC ratios were less than 2, indicating that Algerian honey displayed bactericidal activity on *P. aeruginosa* strains. In the time-kill curve, honey samples (1, 2, 3, 4, and 7) destroyed *P. aeruginosa* after 24 hours of incubation, with honey samples 5 and 6 destroying the bacterium after 21 hours of incubation. The anti-biofilm effect revealed that all tested honey samples effectively inhibited biofilm formation with percentages varying from 54.32% to 97.48%.

In conclusion, Algerian honey can be effective as an alternative antibacterial agent for the treatment of infected wounds, especially those caused by *P. aeruginosa*.

Key words

antibacterial activity, biofilm, alternative treatment, honey, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, wound infections

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Introduction

In infected wounds, activated leukocytes release cytolytic enzymes, free radicals, oxygen, and inflammatory mediators. These cause an imbalance between local pathological factors and the integrity of immune defenses.¹ This promotes the colonization of wounds by pathogenic bacteria, including *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, which has become an important cause of morbidity and mortality in recent years, particularly in immunocompromised patients.² There are several types of virulence factors in *P. aeruginosa*, including pili, exoenzyme S, and other non-pili adhesins that reinforce adhesion to epithelia. Exotoxin A is responsible for severe inflammation and tissue necrosis, while phospholipase C causes tissue damage. However, exoenzyme S is involved in the disruption of cytoskeletal organization and the destruction of immunoglobulin G and A. In addition, *P. aeruginosa* produces at least

four proteases causing hemorrhage and tissue necrosis and it secretes siderophores (pyoverdine and pyochelin) to multiply in the absence of free iron.^{3,4} Moreover, *P. aeruginosa* is characterized by genetic flexibility enabling it to develop resistance to antimicrobial agents. This leads to the emergence of multidrug resistant *P. aeruginosa* in the hospital environment.⁴ Indeed, *P. aeruginosa* is among the first bacterial species incriminated in wound infections. It is responsible for additional morbidity and mortality, prolonged length of stay, and increased cost of hospitalization.^{5,6} Recently, the emergence of multidrug-resistant *P. aeruginosa* has attracted significant attention from medical professionals in Algeria,⁷⁻⁹ particularly in the hospital environment, where, if not controlled, it could evolve into a life-threatening situation.¹⁰ It has been demonstrated that the most important factor that makes *P. aeruginosa* tolerant to antimicrobial agents is its ability to form biofilms; these

have been described as “*surface-attached microbial communities* of bacterium enclosed in a protective polysaccharide matrix with characteristic architecture and phenotypic and biochemical properties distinct from their free-swimming, planktonic counterparts”.¹¹ The extracellular matrix is thought to retain these communities and contributes to the persistence of bacteria at the sites of infection by protecting them from the host’s immune system and antimicrobial stresses.¹² Recently, it has been emphasized that bacterial biofilm plays an important role in chronic wounds, particularly in the context of the prolongation of the inflammatory phase of repair.^{12,13} They interfere with the natural healing process by acting as a mechanical barrier, which prevents reepithelialization, stimulating a chronic state of inflammation, and providing protection against antimicrobial agents.¹³ Since biofilm makes the treatment of infected wounds ineffective, thereby extending hospital stay, inflating management cost and worsening outcomes, the need for new antimicrobial agents has increased. Great attention is paid to natural products, among which honey is described as a very effective means against several types of infections,^{14,15} particularly, wound infections.^{16,17} Antibacterial activity of honey is associated with a combination of several components such as hyperosmolarity, acidity, hydrogen peroxide, and other factors including lysozyme, phenolic acids, and flavonoids. Honey is effective in

treating infected wounds by reducing wound surface area and stimulating healing.¹⁸ In addition, honey can maintain a wound in a healthy state through the wound debridement process and increase collagen synthesis.¹⁹ Nonetheless, the quality of honey may vary depending on the geographical floral origin, season, environmental factors, and storage conditions.²⁰

Algeria is an African country that occupies the north-center of the continent; it is characterized by highly diversified forest ecosystems.²¹ There are approximately 4300 plant species of which 15% are endemic.²² This potential for medicinal plants leads to the production of natural honey rich in bioactive phytochemical compounds. However, very few studies have been conducted on Algerian honeys. Therefore, in this study, we aimed to evaluate the antibacterial and anti-biofilm effects of seven Algerian honey types against forty *clinical strains* of *P. aeruginosa* isolated from infected wounds and the standard strain *P. aeruginosa* PAO1.

Materials and methods

Tested Honey

Seven multiflora honey samples from *Apis mellifera* were obtained from bee farms in different geographical regions of north-eastern Algeria (Table 1). All

Table 1 Botanical and geographical locations of the harvested honey.

Honey sample	Floral source	City	Geographical region
1	<i>Eucalyptus, Pinus</i>	El Taref	Extreme north-eastern Algeria
2	<i>Thymus hirtus</i> <i>Ruta graveolens</i> , <i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i>	Setif	East of Algeria
3	<i>Quercus, Castanea</i>	Jijel	North-eastern Algeria
4	<i>Rosmarinus officinalis</i> , <i>Thymus, Ecballium elaterium</i> , <i>Lonicera caprifolium</i>	Tebessa	East of Algeria
5	<i>Ruta graveolens, Pituranthos scoparius</i> , <i>Thymus vulgaris</i>	Batna	East of Algeria
6	<i>Thymus hirtus</i> , <i>Marrubium vulgare</i>	M’Sila	The central part of north Algeria
7	<i>Ziziphus, Artemisia</i>	Djelfa	The central part of north Algeria

seven honey samples were raw, natural, and had not been exposed to heat; they were collected in sterile dark glass bottles. Each honey sample was first filtered with a sterile filter of 0.22 μm pore sizes (Millipore, Nunc, Paramus, NJ, USA) and stored at 2-8 °C until used. The following honey dilutions were prepared in sterile distilled water: 2.5%, 5%, 10%, 20%, 40%, 80% (w/v) and undiluted honey.

Tested bacterial strains

Forty clinical strains of *P. aeruginosa* were used; these strains were isolated from infected wounds from two hospitals (Ibn Sina and Ibn Rochd Hospitals, Annaba, Algeria). The identification was done by using microbiological and biochemical methods including Gram staining, oxidase, and catalase tests, growth in King A and King B medium, analytical profile index (API) 20NE (Biomerieux, Paris, France). According to their antibiotic resistance profile, only strains that had shown multidrug resistance were selected. Tested antibiotics are those commonly used for the treatment of *P. aeruginosa* infections including ticarcillin, ticarcillin-clavulanic acid, piperacillin, ceftazidime, cefepime, cefazolin, aztreonam, imipenem, tobramycin, amikacin, ciprofloxacin, polymyxin B, and fosfomycin. In addition, a standard strain *P. aeruginosa* PAO1 was used as a positive control. An inoculum of each tested bacterium of 10^6 colony-forming units (CFU)/mL was prepared in nutrient broth (Difco, MD, USA).

Antibacterial activity

Agar well diffusion assay

The agar well diffusion assay was performed according to the method described previously by Al-Kafa-ween, (2019).²³ Briefly, wells of 6 mm of diameter were created in Mueller Hinton agar plates (Difco, MD, USA). Then, the plates were inoculated by spreading a volume of the microbial inoculum on the whole surface of the agar. Next, a volume of 100 μL of tested honey is introduced into the well. A well filled with sterile distilled water was used as a negative control. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. The antibacterial activity of the honey samples was compared based on the inhibition diameters around the wells.

Micro-broth dilution assay

The microdilution test was performed according to the method previously described by Boorn et al. (2010) using sterile 96-well microtiter plates (Fisher Scientific, UK). A volume of 100 μL of the inoculum of the tested bacterium is added to 100 μL of honey at different concentrations (from 2.5 to 100%) in each well. Two wells are used as controls; one well filled with 200 μL of honey was used as a negative control.

Another well filled with 200 μL of inoculum is used as bacterial growth control. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) is the lowest concentration of honey required to inhibit bacterial growth.²⁴

For each honey type, the MIC50% and MIC90% were calculated using the geometric formula:

$$\text{MIC}_{50} = \text{MIC}_a + ((n - a) (\text{MIC}_b - \text{MIC}_a) / b)$$

Where:

MIC_a: MIC of the highest cumulative percentage below 50%,

MIC_b: MIC of the lowest cumulative percentage above 50%.

n: 50% of the number of tested bacteria.

a: number of bacteria in the group at MIC_a

b: number of the bacteria in the group at MIC_b

MIC₉₀ was calculated as the same method of MIC₅₀ where 'n' represents 90% of the number of tested bacteria.^{25,26}

The minimum bactericidal concentration (MBC) was determined by cultivating a volume of 10 μL of all wells that have not shown growth. The Petri dishes were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours. MBC is the lowest concentration of honey required to kill 99% of the tested bacterial strains.²⁷ For each honey sample, the MBC values and the MBC/MIC ratio were determined and used to classify honey samples as bacteriostatic or bactericidal honey.

Time-kill analysis

Time-kill assay was performed to evaluate the effect of honey on the growth and viability of *P. aeruginosa*. One tube of diluted honey 40 % (w/v) at a volume of 2 mL was inoculated with 0.02 mL of bacterial inoculum at approximately 10^6 CFU/mL. Another tube of inoculated nutrient broth without honey was used as a positive control. The tubes were incubated in dark at 37°C with constant shaking at 200 rpm. Bacterial growth was quantified every three hours during 24 hours. Broth aliquots were collected, cultivated on agar nutrient, and incubated for 24 hours at 37°C to determine the total CFU/mL. Honey samples were considered bactericidal when a decrease in CFU compared with the initial inoculum (control without honey) was observed. The Percentage of inhibition of each honey was calculated by the following formula:²⁸

$$\text{Percentage of inhibition (\%)} = 1 - \left[\frac{T1_{\text{treatment}} - T0_{\text{treatment}}}{T1_{\text{control}} - T0_{\text{control}}} \right] * 100$$

Where:

T0 treatment: Absorbance of the test at 0 hour.

T1 treatment: Absorbance of the test at T1 (after every 3 hours).

T0 control: Absorbance of control at 0 hours.

T1 control: Absorbance of control at T1 (after every 3 hours).

Anti-biofilm assay

Initially, *P. aeruginosa* strains were screened for their adherence profile to polystyrene microtiter plate wells according to the method described previously by Al-Kafaween (2019).²⁹ Then, the anti-biofilm effect of honey samples was determined against the three strains of *P. aeruginosa* with a strongly adherent profile. Fresh tryptone soya broth (Difco, MD, USA) was added to an overnight culture of *P. aeruginosa* to adjust its turbidity to achieve a cell density of 10^6 CFU/mL.

The microplates were inoculated with 100 μ L of the bacterial suspension and 100 μ L of honey at 40% (w/v). A well inoculated with the bacterial suspension was used as a positive control; another well filled with tryptone soya broth was used as a negative control. After incubation for 24 hours at 37° C, the wells were gently aspirated and then washed three times with sterile phosphate-buffered saline. To fix the adherent cell, aliquots of 200 μ L of methanol were added and left for 20 min. The wells were stained with 200 μ L of crystal violet (2%) for 20 min and the unbound dye was removed under running distilled water and dried in air. The bound dye was eluted by adding 160 μ L of ethanol and the optical densities (OD) of the stained

adherent biofilms were detected at a wavelength of 550 nm.³⁰ The test was repeated three times, and the average of the optical densities was calculated. The percentage of biofilm reduction was calculated according to this formula:

$$\text{Percentage of biofilm reduction(\%)} = \frac{\text{OD}_{\text{positive control}} - \text{OD}_{\text{treatment}}}{\text{OD}_{\text{positive control}}} \times 100$$

Statistical analysis

The results obtained were analyzed by GraphPad Prism version 7.00 for Windows, (GraphPad Software, La Jolla California USA). The statistical analysis was determined by a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by a post hoc Tukey test to estimate the differences in antibacterial activity between honey samples.

Results and discussion

Well diffusion assay

The results of the inhibitory diameters of tested honey samples are summarized in Figure 1. All honey samples have shown a good antibacterial effect on *P. aeruginosa* strains, the averages of inhibitory diameters are in the range between 14.65 ± 3.88 mm to 28.02 ± 3.19 mm. Honey sample 5 has shown the best antibacterial activity, this is could be due to the bioactive phytochemicals from medicinal plants (*Ruta graveolens*, *Pituranthos scoparius*, and *Thymus vulgaris*).

Figure 1 Mean of the inhibitory diameters (\pm S.D mm) of seven Algerian honey samples against *P. aeruginosa* strains isolated from wound infections.

There are no significant differences between means that have the same letter ($P = 0,053$), but there are highly significant differences between means that have different letters.

MIC and MBC Determination

The results of MIC and MBC are reported in table 2. The MIC values ranged from 10 to 40 % (w/v). The MIC₅₀ ranged from 7.88 to 18.5% (w/v) and MIC₉₀ varied between 18.78 and 38.35 % (w/v). These results demonstrated that all honey samples are effective against *P.aeruginosa* from infected wounds. Agbagwa and colleagues have reported that Nigerian honey has smaller inhibitory diameters than Algerian honey (3-9 mm).³¹ In other studies, Mandal and Mandal have reported that Indian honey has comparable MIC values, which ranged from 8.25 to 25 % (v/v). Also, Shenoy and colleagues have reported that multifloral honey has MIC values between 15 to 25 % (v/v).³² Furthermore, Henriques and colleagues have reported that the MIC of Manuka honey is 9.5%.³³ It has been demonstrated previously that all honey samples haven't the same antibacterial activity.^{34,35} Many authors have shown that the differences in the antimicrobial effect among the different honey samples depend on its geographical, seasonal and botanical source as well as harvesting, processing, and storage condition.^{15,20,37} The difference in the antibacterial activity of Algerian honey samples is related to the difference in geographical and botanical localities. Algerian botanical flora is well known for its diversity; this contributes to producing a good quality honey.^{14,15,20}

The MBC values are ranged from 22.44 (\pm 6.62) for honey sample 5 to 39.51 (\pm 8.35) % (w/v) for honey sample 3. Indeed, MBC/MIC ratios are determined to define the bactericidal or bacteriostatic effect of an antibacterial agent. According to O'Neill et Chopra, when the MBC/MIC ratio is less than or equal to 4, the antimicrobial agent has a bactericidal effect,³⁶ therefore, all tested honey samples exhibit a bactericidal

effect on *P. aeruginosa* strains because the MBC/MIC ratios of all honey samples were less than 4.

Time-kill assay

To verify the impact of honey on the viability of *P.aeruginosa*, a time-kill curve was conducted. As shown in figure 2, most of the strains (73.17 %) are inhibited after 9 hours of growth by honey. After the first 24 hours of incubation, honey had destroyed all tested strains. According to Molan, the bactericidal effect of honey is dependent on the time of honey action and the bacterial species; it varies from several to 40 hours.³⁷ Moreover, the concentration of honey also plays an important role. These results are in agreement with those of Wilkinson and Cavanagh who studied the efficacy of 13 kinds of honey on *P. aeruginosa* demonstrating that all honey samples had a bactericidal effect. Jantakee and Tragoolpua have also reported that honey at concentrations from 5 to 50% is bactericidal. Furthermore, Shenoy and colleagues have reported that honey at 50 % (w/v) destroys *P. aeruginosa* strains in 24 hours.^{32,38,39}

Anti-biofilm activity

The results of the phenotypic characterization of biofilm production are summarized in table 3. The results showed that 24.5 % of clinical strains of *P. aeruginosa* are non-adherent while 75.5% of strains produce biofilms, of which 7.5% are highly adherent. It is important to mention that the transition from a planktonic to a biofilm growth type is strongly related to bacterial adhesion, this occurs in nature in response to environmental changes.

The inhibitory effect of biofilm formation was evaluated on the three strongly adherent strains and the

Table 2 MIC and MBC (% w/v) determination of seven Algerian honey samples against 40 strains of *P.aeruginosa*.

Honey sample	Range of MIC (% w/v)	Mean of MIC \pm SD (% w/v)	MIC ₅₀ (% w/v)	MIC ₉₀ (% w/v)	Mean of MBC \pm SD (% w/v)	MBC/MIC ratio
1	10-40	23.90 \pm 11.15 ^a	15.95	33.16	34.63 \pm 12.66 ^a	1.45
2	10-40	24.87 \pm 13.44 ^a	16.5	38.35	35.12 \pm 13.98 ^a	1.41
3	10-40	26.34 \pm 13.37 ^a	16.25	38.25	39.51 \pm 8.35 ^a	1.5
4	10-40	19.26 \pm 9.84 ^{a,b}	12.75	23.8	27.32 \pm 9.75 ^b	1.42
5	10-40	15.60 \pm 8.38 ^b	8.54	18.78	22.43 \pm 6.62 ^b	1.43
6	10-40	17.07 \pm 11.23 ^b	7.88	28.28	23.41 \pm 7.61 ^b	1.37
7	10-40	19.02 \pm 11.36 ^b	18.5	35.68	31.22 \pm 10.04 ^a	1.64

Figure 2 The percentage of inhibition of *P. aeruginosa* strains by seven honey samples.

Table 3 Adhesion profiles of the clinical *P.aeruginosa* strains.

Adhesion profile	Number of strains	Percentage of strains (%)
Non-adherent	11	24.5
weekly adherent	5	12.5
moderately adherent	21	55.5
strongly adherent	3	7.5
Total	40	100

Table 4 Percentage of the inhibitory effect of biofilm formation (%) by honey samples against *P. aeruginosa* strains.

Tested strains	Inhibitory effect of biofilm formation (%)						
	Honey 1	Honey 2	Honey 3	Honey 4	Honey 5	Honey 6	Honey 7
<i>P.aeruginosa</i> 1	61.84 ^a	54.32 ^a	69.27 ^a	71.94 ^b	94.12 ^c	54.82 ^a	86.44 ^b
<i>P.aeruginosa</i> 2	54.39 ^a	63.93 ^a	59.87 ^a	76.84 ^b	97.53 ^c	61.62 ^a	84.87 ^b
<i>P.aeruginosa</i> 3	58.61 ^a	56.94 ^a	67.51 ^a	77.17 ^b	96.47 ^c	58.61 ^a	79.40 ^b
<i>P.aeruginosa</i> PAO1	62.31 ^a	57.86 ^a	64.85 ^a	78.32 ^b	97.48 ^c	58.64 ^a	81.67 ^b

There are no significant differences ($P > 0.05$) between honey samples that have the same letters but there are very highly significant differences ($P < 0.0001$) between honey samples that have different letters.

reference strain *P. aeruginosa* PAO1. The results in Table 4 show that all honey samples have given a strong biofilm inhibitory activity, which varied between 54.32 to 97.48%. In addition, Honey 5 has shown more extensive biofilm eradication efficiency than other types of honey.

These results are in agreement with those of similar previous studies.^{30,40} It can be deduced from these results that honey may possess useful therapeutic properties against biofilms formed in infected wounds, in particular, those of *P. aeruginosa*. However, little information is available on the active components in

honey responsible for the anti-biofilm properties. It has been suggested that honey could prevent the development of biofilm either by interfering with bacterial adherence to a surface or by inhibiting the growth of attached cells in the early biofilm stage or by altering the extracellular polymeric substances matrix.⁴¹ In addition, the bactericidal activity of honey may depend on a combination of several factors that can act synergistically to prevent the development of bacterial biofilms in wounds.⁴²

Treatment of infections in wounds must prevent systemic bacterial invasion, sepsis, and biofilm formation.^{42,43} Honey can stimulate the repair of infected wounds. Indeed, it has relevant immunomodulatory properties. It can stimulate monocytes, which are the precursors of macrophages, and induce the secretion of TNF- α . This participates in wound repair mechanisms. Honey could also reduce the release of reactive intermediates, which may limit tissue damage during wound healing.⁴⁴⁻⁴⁷

Conclusion

All honey samples showed good antibacterial and anti-biofilm properties; nevertheless, the multifloral honey number 5 exhibited superior efficacy, originating from an Algerian area (Batna), which is rich in medicinal plants including *Ruta graveolens*, *Pituranthos scoparius*, and *Thymus vulgaris*.

The antibacterial and anti-biofilm properties of honey without risk of bacterial resistance or negative effects, combined with healing and anti-inflammatory effects, could improve the treatment of infected wounds. Further study on the active substances in honey and the molecular mechanism of the antibacterial effects of honey are needed.

Conflict of interest statement

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Περίληψη

Screening of the antibacterial and anti-biofilm effect of multifloral honey against multidrug-resistant *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*

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Στην παρούσα μελέτη, επτά δείγματα αλγερινού μελιού αξιολογήθηκαν για την αντιβακτηριακή τους δράση στην ανάπτυξη, βιωσιμότητα και σχηματισμό βιομεμβράνης κλινικών στελεχών *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* που απομονώθηκαν από μολυσμένα τραύματα.

Η αξιολόγηση της ανασταλτικής δράσης των δειγμάτων μελιού (MIC) προσδιορίστηκε τόσο με δοκιμασία διάχυσης σε άγαρ, όσο και αραιώσεων σε ζυμό. Η επίδραση των δειγμάτων μελιού στη βιωσιμότητα του βακτηρίου *P. aeruginosa* αξιολογήθηκε με τη δοκιμασία βακτηριοκτόνου δράσης (MBC). Το αποτέλεσμα της αναστολής ανάπτυξης βιομεμβράνης πραγματοποιήθηκε με τη χρήση πλακών 96 φρεατίων.

Τα αποτελέσματα έδειξαν ότι το αλγερινό μέλι παρουσιάζει αντιβακτηριδιακή δράση κατά του βακτηρίου *P. aeruginosa*. Οι ανασταλτικές διάμετροι κυμαίνονταν από $14,97 \pm 3,88$ mm έως $27,98 \pm 3,19$ mm. Ωστόσο, οι τιμές MIC κυμάνθηκαν στην περιοχή από 10 έως 40% (w/v). Η MIC₅₀ κυμαινόταν από 7,88 % (w/v) για το δείγμα μελιού 5 έως 18,5% (w/v) για το δείγμα μελιού 7, η MIC₉₀ κυμάνθηκε από 18,78 έως 38,35% (w/v). Οι τιμές MBC κυμαίνονταν από $22,43 \pm 6,62\%$ (w/v) έως $39,51 \pm 8,35\%$ (w/v) και οι αναλογίες MBC/MIC ήταν μικρότερες από 2, γεγονός που δείχνει ότι το αλγερινό μέλι εμφάνισε βακτηριοκτόνο δράση στα στελέχη *P. aeruginosa*. Στην καμπύλη χρόνου-θανάτωσης, τα δείγματα μελιού 1, 2, 3, 4 και 7 έδειξαν θανάτωση του βακτηρίου *P. aeruginosa* μετά από 24 ώρες επώασης, ενώ τα δείγματα μελιού 5 και 6 μετά από 21 ώρες. Η δοκιμασία αναστολής δημιουργίας βιομεμβράνης έδειξε ότι όλα τα δείγματα μελιού που δοκιμάστηκαν ήταν αποτελεσματικά με ποσοστά που κυμαίνονται από 54,32% έως 97,48%.

Συμπερασματικά το αλγερινό μέλι θα μπορούσε να αποτελέσει εναλλακτικό αντιβακτηριδιακό παράγοντα για τη θεραπεία μολυσμένων τραυμάτων, ειδικά εκείνων που προκαλούνται από *P. aeruginosa*.

Λέξεις κλειδιά

αντιβακτηριδιακή δράση, βιομεμβράνη, εναλλακτική θεραπεία, μέλι, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, μολύνσεις τραυμάτων

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